

GENETIC ANALYSIS OF DRUG-RESISTANT POULTRY BACTERIA AND TOXICITY EVALUATION OF *OCIMUM GRATISSIMUM* METHANOL EXTRACT AS A POTENTIAL ANTIMICROBIAL AGENT

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ABSTRACT

The high prevalence and rising incidence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria in poultry chickens pose a public health risk. This necessitates plant-based antimicrobial compounds with strong therapeutic potential and no side effects associated with synthetic drugs. *Ocimum gratissimum* (Scent leaf) exhibits antimicrobial activity against pathogenic Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacterial strains. The selected bacterial isolates in this study were characterized by molecular methods using 16S rRNA gene sequencing. This study also investigated the acute toxicity profile and *in vivo* protective efficacy of the methanol extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* leaf against selected multidrug-resistant bacterial isolates obtained from poultry chickens. Molecular identification revealed that the selected poultry isolates included *Salmonella enterica* strain BC01, *Escherichia coli* strain g15, *S. flexneri* strain SWHIN_107, *M. morganii* subsp. *Sibonii* strain O60, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strain PL1-RCS238, *Enterobacter aerogenes* strain

KNUC5001, *Proteus mirabilis* strain AYQ-1 16S, *Proteus mirabilis* strain M16, *Serratia marcescens* strain A02, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strain PPA43. Phylogenetic analysis of the obtained gene sequences revealed a very high level of evolutionary similarity between the isolates obtained in this study and those deposited in the NCBI database. The acute toxicity assay of the methanol extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* was found to be 2236.07 mg/kg, while the mouse protection test revealed a strong protective effect, with all test isolates showing 100 % survival over a 5-day period. In conclusion, the *in vivo* effectiveness of *Ocimum gratissimum* extracts against MDR bacteria presents a viable path toward the creation of new treatment options for bacterial infections.

KEYWORDS: *Ocimum gratissimum*, acute toxicity, phylogenetic analysis, poultry-chickens.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The extensive use of antibiotics in poultry farming, primarily for disease prevention, growth promotion, and therapeutic purposes, is a major driver behind the accumulation and dissemination of antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs) within the avian intestinal microbiome.^[1,2] This makes the gastrointestinal system of chickens a major source of antimicrobial-resistant bacteria, endangering the health of poultry and adding to the worldwide antimicrobial resistance (AMR) problem.^[3-6] The complex chicken gut microbiome ecosystem, containing both commensal bacteria and opportunistic pathogens, can acquire and transfer ARGs, endangering human and environmental health and exacerbating public health concerns.

To mitigate the AMR menace, farmers are reducing the use of synthetic antibiotics and focusing on the use of phytonutrients to suppress pathogenic bacteria populations and promote a balanced, healthy chicken microbiome.^[7,8] Phytonutrients contain a diverse array of secondary metabolites, including flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, and phenolics, that act synergistically to improve digestion, boost immunity, and act as safe, natural antimicrobials, curbing AMR in livestock.^[9,10] *Ocimum gratissimum* L., locally called scent leaf, is an aromatic plant whose bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, and terpenoids, reveals their diverse pharmacological properties. These compounds contribute to the plant's antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antimalarial activities, among others, making *O. gratissimum* a versatile medicinal herb.^[11,12]

Mechanistically, *O. gratissimum* extract disrupt microbial cell membranes and interfere with their metabolic processes.^[13,14] However, there is need for rigorous acute toxicity studies to ascertain its safety, potential adverse effects, and establishing safe dosage limits for host/humans. Acute toxicity testing (single-dose studies, LD₅₀ or limit tests) for *O. gratissimum* following the OECD guide will help establish immediate safety limits, identify gross toxic signs and target organs, and provide guide for substance dosing for sub-acute and chronic work.^[15,16]

In vivo studies with animal models offer opportunities for translational knowledge on disease etiology, evaluate the protection efficacy, safety and toxicity measurement of therapeutic substances, and curbs ethical issues with human subjects.^[17] *In vivo* tests are done with doses between minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and acute toxicity (LD50) values to assess safety and efficacy profiles. This study evaluated the acute toxicity profile and protection potentials of the methanol extract of *O. gratissimum* leaf against ten (10) drug-resistant bacterial strains sourced from different poultry samples. It explored its potential as a safe, natural antimicrobial agent.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Molecular Identification of Bacterial Isolates

Ten (10) multi-drug-resistant bacteria isolated from poultry samples (cloacal, nasal, and oral swabs) of layer, broilers, and two-week-old chicks were used for this study. These swaps were taken from six randomly settled commercial poultry farms in Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

All isolated bacterial strains were characterized and identified in accordance with standard microbiological protocols, relying on morphological observations and assessment of biochemical characteristics as described by Cheesbrough^[18] and Onuoha *et al.*^[19] Pure cultures were obtained by repeated subculturing on nutrient agar. Pure discrete isolates were subsequently preserved on nutrient agar slants and stored in the refrigerator until further procedures.^[20]

Molecular characterization was performed to confirm the identities of these isolates using the following methods

(a) **Extraction of Genomic DNA:** Genomic DNA was extracted from bacterial isolates using the ZR Fungal/Bacterial DNA Miniprep Kit (Zymo Research) according to the

manufacturer's protocol. Briefly, 2 mL of bacterial broth was lysed in a ZR BashingBead™ Lysis Tube with 750 µL lysis solution and processed at maximum speed for over 5 minutes. After centrifugation, the supernatant of the lysate underwent purification through spin columns, involving sequential steps with specialized buffers for DNA binding, pre-washing, and washing. Finally, the DNA was eluted with 100 µL of DNA elution buffer after a final centrifugation, yielding purified genomic DNA.

(b) Agarose Gel Electrophoresis for DNA and PCR: To create agarose gels, 1 g or 2 g of agarose was mixed with 100 ml TAE buffer, then heated in a microwave until the agarose was fully dissolved, depending on whether DNA or PCR samples were being analyzed. After cooling to about 50 °C, 10 µL EZ Vision DNA stain was added to enable visualization under UV light. The solution was poured into a gel tray, allowed to solidify at 4 °C (10–15 min) or at room temperature (20–30 min). The setup was then placed in an electrophoresis tank filled with 1× TAE buffer. DNA samples or PCR products mixed with a suitable loading buffer were loaded into the wells along with a molecular weight ladder. Electrophoresis was conducted at 80-150V for 1 to 1.5 hours. Subsequently, the gel was placed under a UV transilluminator to reveal the separated DNA fragments as distinct bands.

(c) PCR Amplification of 16SrRNA Gene of the bacterial isolates: The PCR reaction mixture consisted of 12.5 µL Taq Master Mix (New England Biolabs- M0270), 1 µL each of 27F (AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG) and 1525R (AAGGAGGTGWTCCARCCGCA) primers, 2 µL DNA template, and nuclease-free water to reach a total volume of 25 µL.

The DNA samples were loaded onto a PCR machine, and 16SrRNA gene amplification was done. The cycling conditions for amplification of 16SrRNA genes involved initial denaturation carried out at 94°C for 5 mins, followed by 36 cycles of denaturation at 94 °C for 30 seconds, annealing at 56 °C for 30 seconds, and elongation at 72 °C for 45 seconds. This was followed by a final elongation step at 72 °C for 7 minutes and a hold temperature at 10 °C.

2.2 DNA Sequencing Analysis and Phylogenetic Relatedness

Amplified fragments were sequenced using a Genetic Analyzer 3130xl sequencer (Applied Biosystems) to obtain 16S rRNA partial sequences following manufacturers' instructions, while the sequencing kit used was that of the BigDye Terminator v3.1 cycle sequencing kit. The universal Primers as used in the PCR reaction were employed in the initial partial

sequencing. Each pair of the partial sequences obtained was further aligned using Promiga program to enable the designing of the internal primers for complete 16S rRNA gene sequencing.

The sequences were compared with those in the GenBank database using the Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) program for the initial identification of the isolates. Identified isolates were grouped according to their BLAST identities, and the sequences aligned using Molecular Evolution Genetic Analysis (MEGA) X and Bio- Edit software to give the pairwise percentage identity. Isolates with high percentage similarities were considered similar or closely related. Subsequently, the aligned sequences were subjected to phylogenetic analysis using the MEGA X software.

2.3 Acute Toxicity Assay of *Ocimum gratissimum* Methanol Extract

The acute toxicity (LD₅₀) of *Ocimum gratissimum* methanol extract was tested using albino mice weighing between 18.0 and 23.0 grams to determine the lethal dose. The study followed Lorke's^[21] established protocol for determining acute toxicity in mice. All mice were injected intraperitoneally (i.p). This study was carried out in two phases. In the first phase, nine mice were divided into groups of three mice each. Mice from each group were injected with methanol extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* (5000.0 mg/kg, 3000.0 mg/kg, and 1000.0 mg/kg, respectively). The animals were observed for signs and symptoms of toxicity, including mortality within 24 h of administration. In the second phase, nine mice were also divided into groups of three mice each. Mice from each group were injected with the methanol crude extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* (2500.0 mg/kg, 2000.0 mg/kg, and 1500.0 mg/kg, respectively).

The animal models were observed for mortality within 24 h. The LD₅₀ was calculated as \sqrt{AB} , where A is the maximum dose that produced 0 % mortality, and B is the minimum dose that produced 100 % mortality. The interpretation of LD₅₀ was based on the Hodge and Sterner toxicity scale.^[22]

2.4 *In vivo* Antibacterial Activity and Mouse Protection Test of *Ocimum gratissimum*

The antibacterial efficacy and protective effects of *Ocimum gratissimum* extract on MDR bacteria isolates were assessed in mice using the Mouse Protection Test (MPT), described by Ekong *et al.*^[20] This evaluated the crude extract's *in vivo* performance. Mice were divided into groups and inoculated intraperitoneally with 0.5 mL of 18-24 h broth cultures of the

pathogens. The different mouse groups received the extract orally at varying doses (10 %, 20 %, and 30 % LD₅₀) 1 h and 5 h post-infection to test treatment efficacy. However, the control groups received either pathogen broth culture (positive control) or water (negative control), allowing comparison with treated groups.

Animal models had unrestricted food and water for 5 days. Observations of infection signs and survival rates were recorded daily to assess the protective effect of *Ocimum gratissimum* extract.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Informed consent was obtained from commercial poultry farm owners before taking samples from the chicken. The care and use of animals were conducted in accordance with the National Institute of Health Guide for the Use of Laboratory Animals. However, ethical approval for animal use was obtained from the University of Uyo Health Research Ethics Committee to carry out this research.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Poultry and chicken products serve as a major reservoir for various bacteria that cause gastroenteritis, many of which exhibit high levels of antimicrobial resistance, posing serious public health risks worldwide. In this study, bacterial isolates associated with different poultry birds were molecularly identified. Table 1 reveals molecularly verified identities of nine (9) distinct bacterial genera, exhibiting 84-98 % genetic similarity to documented strains. Molecular characterization plays a vital role in elucidating the genetic variability, epidemiological relationships, and antibiotic resistance mechanisms of foodborne pathogens.^[23,24] Molecular characterization enables effective disease surveillance, infection source, and provides insights into the molecular epidemiology of resistant strains. Aside from the insights, molecular techniques, especially PCR, reportedly are rapid, sensitive, specific, and less labor-intensive than conventional techniques.^[25,26]

Routine microbial identification using PCR, targeting species-specific genetic markers like 16S/23S rRNA, enables accurate species identification. This facilitates the use of appropriate antibiotics, ensuring the effective treatment of identified pathogens.^[27-29] Since it allows for crucial understanding of pathogens and their transmission patterns, molecular techniques allow for food safety enhancement and strengthening of public health initiatives. Molecular identification of multidrug-resistant organisms is crucial for comprehending transmission

patterns, enhancing food safety, and strengthening public health initiatives.^[30,31] As part of increasing surveillance of resistant zoonotic pathogens in poultry systems, the results from this study importantly affirm and highlight the need for routine and precise identification for enhanced public health surveillance, control, and safety.

Figures 1-3 illustrate the DNA extraction and PCR amplification process. They show high-quality DNA (Figure 1), amplified 16S rRNA genes (Figure 2), and phylogenetic analysis (Figure 3), revealing genetic relationships among bacterial isolates from poultry chicken parts. The phylogenetic tree shows seven (7) major clades, including *Escherichia coli*, *Escherichia fergusonii*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Morganella morganii*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and the *Salmonella enterica* out-group. The *Escherichia coli* and *Escherichia fergusonii* clade includes *E. coli* strains TCBK21G178, MA12, AJI, CEE12, and isolates with codes 2 and 3 (*Shigella flexneri* and *E. coli*). The phylogenetic tree demonstrates a strong genetic affinity among clade members, as indicated by short branches and tight clustering. This high DNA sequence homology validates their assignment to the *Escherichia* genus, reflecting evolutionary closeness. Including *E. fergusonii* and *Shigella flexneri* with this *E. coli* clade supports their close phylogenetic relationship.

The *Serratia marcescens* clade includes strains jx1, A02, and 9. These isolates show a close phylogenetic connection and are probably variations or subspecies of *S. marcescens* due to their tight clustering and low genetic divergence. The *Klebsiella pneumoniae* clade includes MDR3, Houra Alizadeh-6, 5, and PL1-RCS238 strains. The grouping of these bacterial strains shows a significant degree of similarity and confirms that they are *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The strains 4, 2113, and 17YB9 that make up the *Morganella morganii* clade form a cohesive group, suggesting close relatedness and most likely belong to the same species. The *Proteus mirabilis* clade consists of strains 7, 8, BTPCK6, AYQ-1, M16, and JYDW G5. This cluster shows moderate variation among members of the clade, but all fall under the *Proteus mirabilis* species, suggesting strain-level differences. The strains 10, PPA43, and KHRB-P2 belong to the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* clade. As is typical of same-species clustering, these have very short branch lengths and are tightly clustered.

Strain 1 and CFSAN004344 are members of the *Salmonella enterica* out-group. *Salmonella enterica* exhibits considerable genetic divergence, marked by a lengthy branch (0.873), positioning it as an out-group. This out-group roots the phylogenetic tree, establishing a

directional perspective on the evolutionary connections among the other isolates. The tree topology follows well with established bacterial taxonomy, showing genus and species-level close clusters. This consistency underscores the reliability of 16S rRNA sequencing for resolving phylogenetic relationships and accurate bacterial classifications. This research reveals notable intra-genus diversity as seen within genera like *Proteus* and *Klebsiella*, aligning with prior findings.^[32,33] Such intra-genus variation could stem from ecological plasticity or genetic variability, highlighting the complexity of bacterial evolution.

Different evolutionary rates are indicated by differences in branch length in the phylogenetic tree. *Salmonella's* longer branches indicate higher genetic divergence, possibly due to accelerated mutation rates or longer evolutionary separations, while *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas* exhibit lower evolutionary divergence.^[34] This analysis affirms the utility of 16S rRNA sequencing for evolutionary studies and reinforces previous findings.^[35,36] Collectively, these findings demonstrate the effectiveness of 16S rRNA sequencing in elucidating relationships among bacterial species.

Table 1: Sequence analysis of 16S rRNA genes of the bacterial isolates from poultry-chickens.

Lane	Bacterial Species	Strain Type	Sequence Identity (%)	NCBI Accession Number
1	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	<i>Salmonella enterica</i> strain BC01	98.44	CP129108.1
2	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i> strain g15	89.47	JQ661168.1
3	<i>Shigella flexneri</i>	<i>S. flexneri</i> strain SWHIN_107	96.33	CP055099.1
4	<i>Morganella morganii</i>	<i>M. morganii</i> subsp. <i>Sibonii</i> strain O60	92.6	OQ406007.1
5	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> strain PL1-RCS238	91.84	CP036327.1
6	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i> strain KNUC5001	92.31	JQ682628.1
7	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i> strain AYQ-1 16S	91.77	MH934954.1
8	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i> strain M16	94.76	KT792737.1
9	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	<i>Serratia marcescens</i> strain A02	84.68	OR253741.1
10	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> strain PPA43	93.12	MT300521.1

Figure 1: Gel image of high molecular weight DNA extracted from bacterial isolates.

Figure 2: Gel image showing the amplification of 16S rRNA of the isolates at 1500bp.

Key: Lane M is a 1kb DNA ladder; Lane 1= *Salmonella enterica*; Lane 2= *E. coli*; Lane 3= *Shigella flexneri*; Lane 4= *Morganella morganai*; Lane 5= *Klebsiella pneumonia*; Lane 6= *Enterobacter aerogenes*; Lane 7= *Proteus mirabilis*; Lane 8= *Proteus mirabilis*; Lane 9= *Serratia marcescens*, and Lane 10= *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

Figure 3: Phylogenetic tree between 16S rRNA sequences.

These isolates cluster tightly, with minimal genetic divergence, indicating they are likely variants or subspecies of *S. marcescens* and reflecting a strong phylogenetic relationship. The *Klebsiella pneumoniae* clade includes strains MDR3, Houri Alizadeh-6, 5, and PL1-RCS238. These strains are grouped, indicating high similarity and confirming their identity as *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The *Morganella morganii* clade consists of strains 4, 2113, and 17YB9, which form a coherent group, indicating that the isolates are closely related and likely belong to the same species. The *Proteus mirabilis* clade consists of strains 7, 8, BTPCK6, AYQ-1, M16, and JYDW G5. This cluster shows moderate variation among strains, but all fall under the *Proteus mirabilis* species, suggesting strain-level differences. The *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* clade consists of strains 10, PPA43, and KHRB-P2. These are very closely related, with very short branch lengths, typical of same-species clustering. The *Salmonella enterica* out-group contained strain 1 and CFSAN004344. *Salmonella enterica* strains are highly divergent from the rest of the isolates, as indicated by the Long Branch length (0.873). This suggests these strains serve as an out-group, used to root the tree and give directionality to the evolutionary relationships.

The result of the acute toxicity of methanol *Ocimum gratissimum* extract is presented in Table 2. The LD₅₀ was determined to be 2236.07 mg/kg. Doses above 2500 mg/kg resulted in 100 % mortality, while doses at or below 2000 mg/kg were non-lethal, establishing a toxicity threshold for the extract in mice. Based on Hodge and Sterner's toxicity scale on Table 3, this finding suggests that methanol *Ocimum gratissimum* extract with an LD₅₀ of 2236.07 mg/kg was practically non-toxic.

Table 2 summarizes the acute toxicity findings of *Ocimum gratissimum* methanol extract. The LD₅₀ was determined to be 2236.07 mg/kg; doses exceeding 2500 mg/kg were lethal, while those under 2000 mg/kg proved safe. This data established a clear toxicity threshold for the extract in murine models. According to Hodge and Sterner's toxicity classification (Table 3), the methanol *Ocimum gratissimum* extract's LD₅₀ of 2236.07 mg/kg categorizes it as practically non-toxic. The *in vivo* antibacterial activity and mouse protection efficacy of the methanol extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* against MDR bacteria, presented in Table 4, revealed a strong protective effect in mice models. The extract demonstrated a 100 % survival rate in mice models infected with various bacteria, including *Salmonella enterica*, *Shigella flexneri*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Proteus mirabilis* over 5 days. No fatalities were observed, suggesting the

extract's potential protective effects against these pathogens. Results from this study align with a retrospective study where *O. gratissimum* extracts exhibited only mild toxicity at higher doses in albino rats.^[37]

Another study with an LD₅₀ greater than 5000 mg/kg in Wistar rats reported no behavioral disturbances or mortality in acute studies,^[38] while another found no mortality or significant adverse effects in mice at doses up to 2000 mg/kg.^[39] This indicates that *O. gratissimum* extract can be considered safe for oral administration. Additional studies with plant extracts (alkaloids, glycosides, saponins, tannins, and anthraquinones) support the safety and therapeutic value of plant extracts.^[40,41] These findings show no adverse effects at high doses and improved survival in animal models infected with bacteria, aligning with the current study's results.

Table 2: Acute Toxicity (LD₅₀) of Methanol *Ocimum gratissimum* Extract.

Test Group	No of Mice	Dose	No of Death	% Mortality
1	3	5000	3	100
2	3	3000	3	100
3	3	2500	3	100
4	3	2000	0	0
5	3	1500	0	0
6	3	1000	0	0

LD₅₀ = \sqrt{AB} Where A = Maximum dose that gave no mortality; B = minimum dose that produced 100 % mortality

$$\sqrt{2000 \times 2500} = \sqrt{5000} = 2236.07 \text{ mg/kg.}$$

Table 3: Classification of LD₅₀ based on Hodge and Sterner's toxicity scale.

Group	LD ₅₀	Classification
1	<5 mg/kg	Extremely toxic
2	5-50 mg/kg	Highly toxic
3	50-500 mg/kg	Moderately toxic
4	500-5000 mg/kg	Slightly toxic
5	5000-50000 mg/kg	Practically non-toxic
6	>15000 mg/kg	Relatively harmless

Table 4: *In vivo* Antibacterial Activity and Mouse Protection Efficacy of Methanol Extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* against MDR Gastroenteric Bacteria.

Test isolates	Number of mice	No. of deaths within 5 days						No. of survivors within 5 days	Percentage death	Percentage protection
		1	2	3	4	5	Total			
SE	9	-	-	-	-	-	0	9	0.00	100.00
SF	9	-	-	-	-	-	0	9	0.00	100.00
KP	9	-	-	-	-	-	0	9	0.00	100.00

EC	9	-	-	-	-	-	0	9	0.00	100.00
EA	9	-	-	-	-	-	0	9	0.00	100.00
PA	9	-	-	-	-	-	0	9	0.00	100.00
PM	9	-	-	-	-	-	0	9	0.00	100.00

4.0 CONCLUSION AND FURTHER STUDY POINTS

This study provides insight on the growing concern of MDR bacteria in poultry and proposes *Ocimum gratissimum* as a viable alternative antibacterial agent for chemotherapy of poultry infections and diseases. The methanol extract proved safe at lower (≤ 2000 mg/kg) doses and effectively combated MDR pathogens *in vivo*, suggesting it as a promising candidate for therapeutic applications against MDR pathogens from poultry-chickens.

Ocimum gratissimum's efficacy and safety profile makes it a complementary or alternative therapy in poultry health management, reducing reliance on conventional antibiotics and mitigating the risk of further resistance development. Further research could explore optimal dosage, administration methods, and large-scale application of this plant extract in agricultural settings.

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Competing Interests

The Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Author Contributions

IAI: carried out the laboratory investigations and wrote the first draft of the manuscript USE: designed and supervised the work ODA, UA and NSU: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Data curation. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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